

**IMPLEMENTATION OF ANTI-STRATEGIC LAWSUIT AGAINST
PUBLIC PARTICIPATION (ANTI-SLAPP) MECHANISM:
ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE AND ENVIRONMENTAL LAW IN THE
FRAMEWORK OF ACHIEVING SGDS 2030**

Khalisah Hayatuddin^{1*}, Nahla Jamilie Rahmah Mukhtarudin², Cika Pidiani³

^{1,2,3}Faculty of Law, Universitas Muhammadiyah Palembang
Corresponding Author: nahlamukhtarudin95@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the implementation of the Anti-Strategic Lawsuit Against Public Participation (Anti-SLAPP) mechanism within Indonesia's environmental law enforcement framework, particularly in the context of National Strategic Projects (PSN), which often generate environmental and social conflicts. Employing a normative juridical method with a statute approach and conceptual approach, the research examines primary legal sources, including Law No. 32/2009 on Environmental Protection and Management, Supreme Court Regulation No. 1/2023, and relevant court decisions concerning the criminalization of environmental defenders. Secondary legal sources—such as academic journals, books, and research institution reports—are used to strengthen the analytical basis of this study. The findings indicate that Article 66 of the Environmental Law and the judicial guidelines under Perma No. 1/2023 serve as crucial safeguards that protect public participation from intimidation, particularly in environmental monitoring and permitting processes such as AMDAL. However, substantial challenges remain in practice, including regulatory disharmony, limited capacity among law enforcement institutions, and strong economic-political pressures embedded in development policies. Additionally, public participation mechanisms often remain procedural rather than substantive, while dispute resolution systems have yet to fully guarantee equality and effective remedies for affected communities. This study concludes that strengthening Anti-SLAPP regulations, enhancing legal literacy, and reforming environmental dispute resolution mechanisms are essential prerequisites for achieving environmental justice and supporting the fulfillment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030 in Indonesia.

Keywords: *Anti-SLAPP, Environmental Law Enforcement, Environmental Justice, National Strategic Projects (NSP), Public Participation.*